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Мовна особистість правника: компетентності як основа формування

Галдецька Ірина Григорівна

кандидат юридичних наук, доцент, професор кафедри мовної підготовки,
Національна академія внутрішніх справ, м. Київ, Україна

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4887-3655>

Драмарецька Лариса Борисівна

старший викладач кафедри мовної підготовки,
Національна академія внутрішніх справ, Київ, Україна

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4839-7740>

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***Анотація:** У статті досліджено роль мовної, мовленнєвої та комунікативної компетентностей у процесі професійної підготовки майбутніх юристів в умовах модернізації української освіти та трансформації правової системи. Визначено, що мовна компетентність забезпечує знання норм української мови та здатність їх адекватно застосовувати у правничому дискурсі; мовленнєва компетентність виявляється в умінні чітко, логічно й переконливо формулювати думки в усній і письмовій формах; комунікативна компетентність передбачає здатність до конструктивного діалогу, ефективної взаємодії в професійному середовищі та дотримання етичних принципів спілкування. Підкреслено, що саме через мовлення реалізується професійна компетентність юриста – у публічних виступах, переговорах,*

підготовці нормативно-правових актів і процесуальних документів. Узагальнено, що формування мовної, мовленнєвої та комунікативної компетентностей є стратегічним завданням юридичної освіти, оскільки воно забезпечує якість правничої діяльності, сприяє розвитку правової культури суспільства та формує позитивний професійний імідж сучасного юриста. Запропоновано шляхи вдосконалення освітнього процесу – розширення навчальних програм за рахунок курсів із риторики, культури професійного мовлення та ефективної комунікації, а також упровадження тренінгів і семінарів, спрямованих на розвиток професійного мовлення й комунікативної культури майбутніх правників.

Ключові слова: *культура мовлення, мовна компетентність, мовленнєва компетентність, комунікативна компетентність, комунікативні навички, правнича освіта, професійна етика, професійна культура юриста, правове спілкування, юридична діяльність.*

The Lawyer's linguistic personality: competencies as the foundation of development

Haldetska Iryna Hryhorivna

PhD in Law, Associate Professor, Professor of the Department of Language Training,
National Academy of Internal Affairs, Kyiv, Ukraine

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4887-3655>

Dramaretska Larysa Borysivna

senior lecturer of the Department of Languages Training,
National Academy of Internal Affairs, Kyiv, Ukraine

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4839-7740>

***Abstract:** The article examines the role of linguistic, speech, and communicative competencies in the professional training of future lawyers in the context of the modernization of Ukrainian education and the transformation of the legal system. It is determined that linguistic competence ensures knowledge of the norms of the Ukrainian language and the ability to apply them adequately in legal discourse; speech competence manifests itself in the ability to formulate thoughts clearly, logically, and convincingly in oral and written forms; communicative competence implies the ability to engage in constructive dialogue, effective interaction in a professional environment, and adherence to ethical principles of communication. It is emphasized that it is through speech that the professional competence of a lawyer is realized – in public speeches, negotiations, preparation of normative-legal acts and procedural documents. It is summarized that the formation of linguistic, speech, and communicative competencies is a strategic task of legal education, as it ensures the quality of legal activity, contributes to the development of the legal culture of society, and forms a positive professional image of a modern lawyer. Ways to improve the educational process are proposed, including expanding curricula with courses in rhetoric, professional speech culture, and effective communication, as well as introducing training sessions and seminars aimed at developing the professional speech and communication culture of future lawyers.*

***Keywords:** speech culture, linguistic competence, speech competence, communicative competence, communication skills, legal education, professional ethics, professional culture of a lawyer, legal communication, legal practice.*

Problem statement. At the current stage of development of Ukrainian society, large-scale transformation processes are taking place, aimed at establishing Ukraine as a democratic, legal and social state. Systemic reforms cover various spheres of public life, among which the modernisation of the legal sector occupies a special place. It is designed not only to ensure the effective functioning of the institutions of

the legal system, but also to create a new model for training future legal professionals who are able to meet the demands of the times and public expectations. The needs of modern society, driven by profound economic, political and cultural changes, are shaping new benchmarks in the system of professional education and training. Future representatives of the legal profession are required not only to have a thorough knowledge of the law and the ability to apply it, but also a high level of social, ethical and communication skills. Today's lawyer is not only a bearer of legal knowledge, but also an active participant in social interaction, embodying the moral and cultural values of their society and reflecting its level of legal awareness and legal culture.

A lawyer today is not merely a bearer of legal knowledge but an active participant in social interaction who embodies the moral and cultural values of their society and reflects the level of its legal consciousness and legal culture.

Undoubtedly, an essential component of a lawyer's professional activity is their professional and communicative culture, which ensures the effectiveness of interaction across various types of legal practice. It is through speech that a lawyer's professional competence is realized – in the process of public speaking, conducting negotiations and dialogues, drafting regulatory and legal documents, preparing procedural materials, interpreting legal norms and texts.

The communicative culture of a lawyer serves not only as an instrument of professional influence but also as an important factor in fostering public trust in the legal system as a whole.

It should be noted that lawyers, in the course of their professional activity, constantly interact with representatives of various social groups, professional communities, and cultural environments. Under such conditions, the ability to choose an appropriate communicative strategy, select suitable linguistic means, present one's position in a well-reasoned manner, and structure thoughts logically constitutes a key characteristic of a lawyer's professional culture [4, p. 248].

Thus, the training of future lawyers in the context of contemporary reforms requires a rethinking of traditional approaches to the formation of their professional culture. The emphasis should be shifted toward the development of communicative competence as one of the fundamental components of professionalism, which determines the success of professional activity and influences the overall level of legal culture within society.

Analysis of the current research. The last decades are characterized by a noticeable increase in scientific interest in the problem of formation of language, speech and communicative competences among representatives of the legal profession. The issues of professional speech of a lawyer, its specifics, structure and role in the system of professional training are considered in the works of many Ukrainian researchers. In particular, Y. Korotkova, O. Novikova and I. Kozubenko analyze the features of professional legal speech, outline its functions in modern socio-communicative conditions and develop theoretical foundations of the concept of the culture of speech of a lawyer. Their research emphasizes the need to form speech literacy as a component of the general culture of a lawyer, which directly affects the effectiveness of law enforcement activities [7; 8; 10].

The issues of language training of future lawyers are thoroughly covered in the works of N. Artykutsa and I. Yena, who draw their attention to the search for innovative ways to improve the language competence of law students. The researchers emphasize that high-quality language education ensures the formation of the ability to adequately use language resources in professional communication, which is the key to the communicative success of a specialist.[1; 6].

Shestakova S. considers the issue of professional communication of law enforcement officials in the context of a modern innovative paradigm. The author emphasizes the importance of integrating the latest information and communication technologies into the practice of law enforcement communication, which contributes

to increasing the level of mutual understanding between participants in the legal process [12].

The studies of Kovalenko O. and Varieshkina N. focus on the issue of mastering foreign languages as a necessary condition for a lawyer's professional development in the context of the globalization of the legal sphere. The researchers emphasize that proficiency in a foreign language not only broadens a specialist's professional opportunities but also provides access to international legal sources, thereby facilitating integration into the global legal community [4; 9]. The issue of forming professional speech competence of future law enforcement officers is studied by L. Baranovska and S. Tsyhanii. Their works identify the main criteria for the effective development of speech skills, describe the methodological principles of speech training for students of legal specialties, and outline practical approaches to improving the culture of professional communication [3].

Despite the considerable attention paid by scholars to this issue, it should be noted that the question of improving the culture of legal speech in the context of contemporary social transformations requires further theoretical consideration. Of particular relevance is the consideration of the linguistic and professional aspects of legal practice, taking into account contemporary requirements and professional standards that define the image of a lawyer as a highly qualified, communicatively competent specialist. In addition, it is relevant to study the reflection of the speech culture of lawyers in the regulatory framework, which should regulate the standards of professional conduct, ethics, and communication in the field of jurisprudence.

A significant contribution to this field has also been made by the authors of contemporary monographs and textbooks that model the structure of communicative competence and define the pedagogical conditions for its development in the legal education system (Department of Law and Public Administration). A separate group of studies consists of works devoted to speech competence in specific professional contexts: the development of speech skills during the formation of a lawyer

(Chornobai), communicative aspects of the activities of judges (Pivovarov, Fivkin). These works emphasize the influence of a lawyer's level of linguistic culture on the quality of law enforcement and the effectiveness of the judicial process [11; 13].

Special attention should be paid to studying the linguistic and professional aspects of a lawyer's work in the context of contemporary social transformations, particularly under the influence of martial law and the digitization of communications (works by Pivovarov and Fivkin) [11].

The aim of the study is to comprehensively examine the linguistic and professional competencies of lawyers through the prism of regulatory and legal regulation. To achieve this goal, the following main tasks must be accomplished: clarify the content characteristics of the concepts of “competence”, “language competence”, “speech competence”, and “communicative competence”, and determine the interrelationships and mutual influence between them; to determine the role of these categories in the formation of a lawyer's professional personality; to analyze the current regulatory and legal acts that define the modern requirements for a specialist in the legal field; to outline the hierarchy of legal documents in the context of the issue under study – from basic to specialized; to formulate proposals for improving the mechanisms for implementing legislative provisions in the legal education system.

Main body of the study. The issue of linguistic, speech, and communicative competencies of lawyers is becoming particularly important in the context of the reorientation of higher education towards a competency-based model of training specialists. As noted by N. Artykutsa, the language training of future lawyers should be considered not as a secondary component, but as the basis for the professional development of a lawyer. It is linguistic competence that determines the effectiveness of legal activity, since every aspect of law enforcement – from the drafting of procedural documents to court appearances – is realized through speech. The researcher emphasizes that language in the legal sphere is a tool for thinking,

argumentation, and law-making, so the educational process must ensure that students are able to formulate legal judgments clearly and logically. In her opinion, a lawyer's competence is an integrative combination of knowledge, skills, values, and communication skills that allow them to act within the framework of legislative discourse and adhere to the norms of professional ethics. Therefore, according to N.Artykutsa, language training is a key condition for the formation of a professional lawyer who is able to effectively carry out legal activities and maintain high standards of linguistic culture [1. p. 155-157].

Scientists (in particular, O. Novikova, I. Kozubenko) emphasize that the concept of competence encompasses a comprehensive system of acquired means and methods of activity that ensure the effective performance of professional tasks in a particular field. As noted by O. Novikova, competence is not only a set of knowledge and skills, but also an integrated quality of personality that allows a person to flexibly apply them in different situations, creatively modifying them in accordance with the purpose of the activity. In this context, competence is not a static characteristic, but a dynamic system that is formed in the process of cognition, communication, and professional self-improvement. According to modern approaches developed by O. Novikova, language competence is an integral part of professional training, as it involves not only knowledge of normative grammar, orthoepic and stylistic norms, but also the ability to use language appropriately in a professional context [10].

According to I. Kozubenko, Ukrainian professional language culture requires mastery of a system of linguistic norms combined with developed linguistic reflection, which allows specialists to respond appropriately to communicative situations in a professional environment. That is why linguistic competence is considered to be a key element of professional language culture, as it ensures the accuracy, logic, and reasonableness of speech, without which effective legal practice is impossible [7].

Research by I. Yena shows that the linguistic competence of law students is based on the integration of linguistic knowledge and practical skills. It manifests itself through the ability to express oneself effectively in speech and writing, to argue, to interpret normative provisions, and to use language as a tool of professional influence [6]. A similar opinion is expressed by L. Baranovska, who emphasizes that the development of professional and linguistic competence of law enforcement officers is a guarantee of high-quality law enforcement practice [2, p. 118-120].

Contemporary studies pay considerable attention to the development of communicative competence as a complex integrative quality of future legal professionals. According to research by L. Horlova, communicative competence includes language and speech skills, as well as sociolinguistic and discursive awareness, which ensures effective interaction in a professional environment. It is defined not only as the ability to engage in speech activity, but also as a readiness for professional dialogue, the ability to correctly defend one's position, argue decisions, and maintain ethical communication [5, p. 75].

A comparison of the scientific approaches of S. Tsyhanii and N. Shestakova gives grounds to interpret the communicative competence of a lawyer as a structurally multidimensional formation that combines knowledge of language, the ability to use it in legal discourse, and the ability to interact socially. In the works of S. Tsyhanii, communicative competence is considered as an integrative quality of a specialist, which includes linguistic, speech, sociocultural, and discursive components that ensure effective professional communication within the legal field. On the other hand, N. Shestakova emphasizes the practical dimension of this phenomenon, highlighting the importance of the pragmatic orientation of communication, the ability to adhere to the norms of legal ethics, and to take into account the specifics of communicative situations in professional activity [12, p. 34-35].

At the same time, it is important to note that linguistic, speech, and communicative competences are systematically linked: the first provides knowledge of the language system, the second – the ability to apply this knowledge in the process of generating and perceiving utterances, and the third – the effectiveness and purposefulness of professional communication, which determines the success of legal activity. Thus, a lawyer's communicative competence is not only a means of professional self-expression, but also a tool for effective influence, persuasion, and the achievement of legal justice.

The issue of foreign language training for lawyers is covered in the works of N. Vareshkina, and Yu. Korotkova, who emphasize that proficiency in foreign languages, especially English, is becoming an important component of the communicative competence of legal professionals in the context of globalization. Foreign language competence contributes to the expansion of professional opportunities, access to international legal sources, participation in intercultural discussions, and European legal education programs. Similar ideas can be found in the European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences, which emphasizes the need to integrate language training into the EU legal education system [4; 8].

Domestic researchers, including I. Chornobai, V. Pyvovarov, and O. Fivkin, emphasize the decisive role of a lawyer's linguistic culture in the process of professional development and law enforcement. Scientists emphasize that the linguistic culture of a legal professional is not only an indicator of their education, but also a criterion of professionalism, since it is through language that legal positions are interpreted, formulated, and argued. As noted by I. Chornobai, a lawyer's language skills are an integral tool of their professional activity, ensuring logical thinking, consistency of argumentation, and the ability to convincingly present a legal position in oral and written forms. The position of V. Pivovarov and O. Fivkin deserves special attention, as they emphasize that the level of a judge's linguistic culture directly affects the quality of justice, since the accuracy, correctness, and stylistic

perfection of judicial speech determine both the adequacy of the perception of legal texts and public confidence in court decisions. Legal speech, thus, is considered not only as a technical means of communication, but also as a factor in shaping the professional image of a lawyer and an instrument for implementing the principle of the rule of law [11; 13].

Adding to this, O. Yurchuk points out that modern innovative models of communication in law enforcement are based on the principles of professional ethics, tolerance, clarity, and accuracy of speech. The researcher emphasizes that effective communication by law enforcement officers requires not only the correct use of legal terminology, but also compliance with moral and ethical norms of communication and the ability to interact constructively with different social groups. Therefore, the linguistic culture of a lawyer is a synthesis of professional linguistic competence, communicative flexibility, and ethical responsibility, which together determine the level of their professional skill [14].

The development of language and communication skills in future lawyers has not only an educational but also a legal dimension. According to the Constitution of Ukraine (1996), Ukrainian is the state language, and the state ensures its comprehensive development in all spheres of public life. In the context of legal education, this requirement is specified in the Laws of Ukraine “On Education”, “On Higher Education”, and “On Ensuring the Functioning of the Ukrainian Language as the State Language”. These documents clearly outline the obligation for all professionals whose activities are related to the legal sphere to be proficient in the state language, as well as the importance of learning languages of international communication, primarily English [15; 16; 17].

Legislative norms are consistent with the National Qualifications Framework (CMU Resolution), which stipulates that a higher education graduate must be able to communicate effectively in the state and foreign languages, both orally and in writing. This requirement is specified in the Higher Education Standard for specialty

081 “Law” (MES Order), which includes the ability to communicate in the state and foreign languages among general competencies. Thus, the legislatively enshrined need for language, speech and communicative training of a lawyer is gaining practical implementation in educational programs. Modern legal education in Ukraine is gradually focusing on the integration of professional, language and communicative training, ensuring the unity of theoretical and applied aspects of the formation of a competent lawyer. This corresponds to European trends in the professionalization of legal education, where communicative competence is considered an integral component of professional identity.

In conclusion, it is worth emphasizing that linguistic, speech and communicative competences form a holistic system of a lawyer's professional readiness. They are interdependent and mutually conditioned: linguistic competence provides knowledge, speech – its practical implementation, and communicative – the effectiveness of professional interaction. Their formation, as emphasized by Baranovska, Horlova and Tsyhanii, requires a combination of linguodidactic, psychological and legal approaches aimed at developing a culture of professional speech, communicative ethics and competent linguistic behavior of a future lawyer [3; 5].

Conclusion. The development of linguistic, speech, and communication competencies is a key component of professional training for lawyers in the context of a competency-based education model. Language training ensures not only mastery of the normative basis of the language, but also the ability to formulate legal judgments accurately, logically, and convincingly, which determines the effectiveness of law enforcement.

Together, these competencies create an integrated system of professional readiness: linguistic competence forms knowledge, speech competence ensures its practical application, and communicative competence guarantees effective interaction in the legal environment. They cover not only linguistic skills, but also analytical

thinking, communication culture, and ethical responsibility. Language and communication training for lawyers is also a legally established requirement of the state, which determines its role as a factor of professionalism and a means of implementing the principle of the rule of law. Therefore, the development of these competencies is not only an educational task but also a strategic condition for the formation of a modern lawyer capable of acting effectively, ethically, and convincingly in the legal and social sphere

Taking into account the results of the conducted analysis, it is advisable to propose a set of measures aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of implementing legislative requirements in the field of legal education. First and foremost, it is recommended to expand curricula by increasing the number of instructional hours allocated to the courses “Ukrainian for Professional Purposes” and “English for Professional Purposes.” The bachelor’s degree programs in specialty 081 “Law” should include mandatory courses such as “Rhetoric,” “Culture of Professional Speech,” and “Effective Professional Communication,” which may be taught in both the state (Ukrainian) and English languages.

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